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TAFAKKUR ZIYOSI

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NASHRIYOT
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RETERMINOLOGIZATION OF PHRASEOLOGICAL UNITS IN LINGUISTICS

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Abstract: The main goal of this research is to clarify the reterminologization of phraseological units in linguistics. A number of scientific works have been researched on this topic. The views of different scientists on this concept are given as an example. The study of the reterminologization of phraseological units in linguistics is relevant and important in the modern world, because phraseological units play an important role in linguistics and are an integral part of any language. The task of our research was to clarify the phenomenon of reterminologization in phraseology, in particular, in terminological phraseologisms. The following linguistic and interdisciplinary research methods were used to achieve the goal and fulfill the tasks set in this research work: the method of linguistic description; method of oppositions; methods of communicative linguistics, in particular, the transformational method; semantic method.

Annotatsiya: Mazkur tadqiqotdan ko'zlangan asosiy maqsad – tilshunoslikda frazeologik birliklar reterminologizatsiyasini yoritishdan iborat. Ushbu mavzu bo'yicha bir qator ilmiy ishlar tadqiq qilindi. Mazkur masalaga turli olimlarning qarashlari misol tariqasida keltirilgan. Tilshunoslikda frazeologik birliklarning reterminologizatsiyasini o'rganish zamonaviy dunyoda dolzarb va muhim hisoblanadi, chunki frazeologik birliklar tilshunoslikda muhim rol o'ynaydi va har qanday tilning ajralmas qismi hisoblanadi. Tadqiqotimizning vazifalari sifatida esa frazeologiyada, xususan, terminologik frazeologizmlarda reterminologizatsiya hodisasini yoritish tashkil etdi. Mazkur tadqiqot ishida qo'yilgan maqsadga erishish va belgilangan vazifalarni bajarishda quyidagi tilshunoslik va fanlararo tadqiqot metodlaridan foydalanildi: lisoniy tavsif metodi; oppozitsiyalar metodi; kommunikativ tilshunoslik metodlari, xususan, transformatsion metod; semantik metod.

Аннотация: Основная цель данного исследования – прояснить терминологизацию фразеологических единиц в лингвистике. На эту тему было проведено исследование ряда научных работ. В качестве примера приведены взгляды разных ученых на это понятие. Изучение ретерминологизации фразеологизмов в лингвистике актуально и важно в современном мире, поскольку фразеологизмы играют важную роль в лингвистике и являются неотъемлемой частью любого языка. Задачей нашего исследования было прояснение феномена детерминации во фразеологии, в частности, в терминологических фразеологизмах. Для достижения цели и выполнения задач, поставленных в данной исследовательской работе, были использованы следующие лингвистические и междисциплинарные методы исследования: метод лингвистического описания; метод противопоставлений; методы коммуникативной лингвистики, в частности, трансформационный метод; семантический метод.

Keywords: phrase, phraseology, phraseological units, term, terminology, terminologization, terminologization, structure, semantics, scientific text.

Kalit so'zlar: ibora, frazeologiya, frazeologik birliklar, termin, terminologiya, terminologizatsiya, reterminologizatsiya, tuzilishi, semantika, ilmiy matn.

Ключевые слова: словосочетание, фразеологизм, фразеологические единицы, термин, терминология, терминологизация, терминологизаторство, структура, семантика, научный текст.

It is known that in the 60s of the 20th century, many new terms appeared in the language due to the rapid growth of scientific knowledge. Therefore, the terminological phenomenon has attracted the attention of many linguists and researchers. "Such a sharp change in the

development of terminology was connected with the fact that it began to be considered as a special, rapidly developing lexical system, a composition of the national vocabulary existing according to a certain pattern"¹.

1 Алексеева Л.М. Лингвистика термина// Лексикология. Терминоведение. Стилистика. Сб. научных трудов. Посвящается юбилею В.М.Лейчика. – Москва – Рязань: Пресса, 2003. – 187 с. – С. 37-38

In the 70–80s of the last century the problems of terminology in world linguistics have been studied extensively by V.M.Leychik, K.Y.Averbukh, I.N.Volkova, A.S.Gerd, A.I.Moiseev, E.F.Skorokhod'ko and other scientists. In particular: 1) linguistic description and organization of the essence of the term; 2) automated methods of terminological analysis; 3) analysis of terms in order to create languages for modern information systems; 4) standardization of scientific and technical terminology. The term has united and continues to unite all these fields to this day.

The problems of the impact of terminology on the formation of phraseological units are widely covered in the works of F.P.Filin, F.P.Sorokoletov, V.G.Gak, Y.S.Sorokin² and other scientists. For example, F.P.Filin, talking about special terminology, noted that “a widely used literary language is the most important source of vocabulary expansion”³.

In order to achieve the goal set in this research work and fulfill the set of tasks, based on the problem of reterminologization of phraseological units in contemporary linguistics, a multi-faceted interdisciplinary approach was used to study and describe these units, and the following linguistic and interdisciplinary research methods were used: linguistic description method (terminology in the description and analysis of phraseological units as an object of reterminologization); the method of oppositions (reterminologization of phraseological units); methods of communicative linguistics, in particular, the transformational method (in the analysis of structural or semantic changes of reterminologization of phraseological

units depending on the situation); semantic method (in determining the meaning of phraseological units).

Phraseological units are considered one of the important components of the language, play an important role in communication, enrich the speech and facilitate the delivery of certain semantic content. According to E.N.Dimitrieva, phraseological units can undergo changes and go through terminologization and reterminologization processes. According to the scientist: “Terminologization is the process of phraseological units acquiring a special terminological meaning within a certain field of knowledge or activity. Reterminologization, in turn, is the process of changing the meaning of phraseological units, losing their original meaning and acquiring a new one”⁴. Indeed, language is constantly developing, undergoing a process of evolution, and changes occur. In this process, phraseological units also undergo changes related to their use, expansion and interpretation. One such change is called the reterminologization of phraseological units.

From the point of view of linguistics, it helps to understand the concept of the lexical-semantic system of the whole language by identifying certain semantic and grammatical features of different terminological systems. In his doctoral thesis, A.S.Gerd considers this term as “certain word types, special lexicon and semantic units” and admits that “the uniqueness of the term is not in its expression, but in its structure”⁵.

2 Филин Ф.Н. Истоки и судьбы русского литературного языка. – М.: Наука, 1981. – 327 с.; Сороколетов Ф.П. Терминология и лексикография // Теория языка. Методы его исследования и преподавания. – Л., 1981. – 291 с.; Гак В.Г. Языковые преобразования. – Школа “Языки русской Культуры”. – М., 1998. – 763 с. Сорокин Ю.С. Язык науки и литературный язык//Художественное и научное творчество. – Л.: Паука, 1972. – 215 с.

3 Филин Ф.Н. Истоки и судьбы русского литературного языка. – М.: Наука, 1981. –327 с. – С.183.

4 Димитриева Е. Н. Процессы фразеологизации в английском научно-техническом тексте (на материале LSP “Эксплуатация водного транспорта”: Автореф. дис. канд. филол. наук. – Москва, 2010. – 31 с.

5 Герд А.С. Проблемы формирования научной терминологии (на материале русских научных названий рыб). Автореф. дис. ... д. филол.наук. – Л, 1968. – 26 с. – С.2.

English linguist Lars Gurmund interpreted the terms as “tools used by a particular science”⁶, and at the same time emphasized that the structure of the terminological system of each separate science corresponds to the internal organization of this science.

It should be noted that phraseological units formed with the help of terms are often considered material for studying a certain terminological system. According to F.P.Sorokoletov, “In terms of specific features of semantics, connection with the vocabulary of the common language, and in terms of wide use, the terms related to social and political life occupy a special place, because they enter the free and common speech faster”⁷. The author also acknowledges the expansion of the vocabulary due to space and astronomical terminology.

Nowadays, the process of replenishing the vocabulary or the emergence of new words and the development of new meanings for them is connected not only with the development of new technologies and the emergence of new branches of science and technology, but also with a sharp increase in the volume, quality and multilingualism of communication.

The penetration of terminological expressions into the phraseological system of any language and, at the same time, the reterminologization of phraseological units is one of the most interesting phenomena for modern linguistics. In this research, we consider the issue of phraseological units reterminologization, when phraseological units acquire additional meaning under the influence of certain factors and begin to function as superverbal terms in the language, that is,

phraseological units. In addition, we will analyze the transition of scientific phraseological units to terminology in the case of reterminologization. Before analyzing the reterminologization of scientific phraseological units with the help of examples, it is appropriate to give a definition of this process itself.

As we mentioned above, one of the most active ways of the emergence of terms is the semantic development of a common word, or in other words, terminologization process. This problem in linguistics has recently attracted the attention of Russian linguists such as S.V.Grinev, V.P.Danilenko, L.A.Kapanadze, F.P.Sorokoletov, V.A.Tatarinov, A.N.Shilovskiy, D.N.Shmelev, A.N.Shurygin⁸ and others, although there are already well-known opinions and considerations on this issue in the science, but its solution has not been found et.

Over the years, leading Russian linguists have devoted their works to the close connection between special and general literary languages. In particular, R.A.Budagov in his work “Очерках по языкознанию” recognized that “it is necessary to distinguish between “polysemy” in technical terminology and polysemy in general literary language”⁹. On the influence of the terminological lexicon L.A.Kapanadze noted that “some groups of terms related to the literary language are reinterpreted figuratively and become vivid metaphors”¹⁰.

V.M.Leychik in his article “Термины-фразаологизмы в ряду номинативных словосочетаний терминологического характера”¹¹ developed various criteria for the differentiation of terms and phrases and put

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- 6 Gurmund L. The Problem of Correct Symbolism as Related to Some Problems of Social Psychology. – Goteborg, 1955. – 176 p. – P. 33.
- 7 Сорokoлетов Ф.П. Терминология и лексикография // Теория языка. Методы его исследования и преподавания. – Л., 1981. – 292 с. – С. 250.
- 8 Гринев С.В. Введение в терминоведение. – М.: Московский Лицей, 1993. – 299 с.; Даниленко В.И. Лексико-семантические и грамматические особенности слов-терминов // Исследования по русской терминологии. – М.: Наука, 1971. – 246 с.; Капанадзе Л.А. О понятиях “термин” и “терминология” // История отечественного терминоведения. Том 2. Направления и методы терминологических исследований. Книга 1/ Под. ред. В.А.Татарина. – М.: Московский лицей, – 1999. – 312 с. – С. 42.; Сорokoлетов Ф.П. Терминология и лексикография // Теория языка. Методы его исследования и преподавания. – Л., 1981. – 292 с.; Татаринov В.А. История отечественного терминоведения. Кн. 2. – М.: Московский лицей, 1999. – 357с.; Шмелев Д.Н. Проблемы семантического анализа лексики (на материале русского языка). Автореф. дис. ... д-ра филол. наук. – М., 1969. – 27 с.; Шурьгин Н.А. Семасиологический и лексикографический аспекты таксономизации лингвистических терминов и терминопонятий // Диссертация на соискание ученой степени доктора филологических наук. Тюмень, 2005. – 294 с.
- 9 Будагов Р.А. Очерки по языкознанию. – М.: Изд-во Академии наук, 1953. – 280 с. – 19 с.
- 10 Капанадзе Л.А. О понятиях “термин” и “терминология” // История отечественного терминоведения. Том 2. Направления и методы терминологических исследований. Книга 1/ Под. ред. В.А.Татарина. – М., Московский лицей, – 1999. – 312 с. – 42 с.
- 11 Лейчик В.М. Термины-фразаологизмы в ряду номинативных словосочетаний терминологического характера // Слово. Фраза. Текст. – М.: Азбуковник, 2003. – С. 250 – 261.

forward the actual problem of the transformation of commonly used phraseological units into terms.

Reterminologization of phraseological units is a process of changing the meaning or application of phraseological units in a certain field of knowledge or professional activity. This process can occur as a result of changes in society, scientific discoveries, technological progress and other factors. The fact that phraseological units have new meanings and are used in new contexts and situations can be interpreted as part of reterminologization. It can happen spontaneously or consciously, and as a result, the language is updated and developed.

Based on the above definitions, we can say that the reterminologization of phraseological units is the process of losing the specific meaning of phraseological units and passing them into the universal vocabulary. As a result of such a phenomenon, phraseological units lose their uniqueness and can be used without any obstacles in different situations and contexts. For example:

For example, the English phraseological unit acid test¹² expresses the following meaning:

1) Chemical term – Any crucial or conclusive test to judge value or genuineness; the “real” test. The term is an extension of a chemical test using nitric acid or aqua fortis, as it is sometimes called, to determine the gold content of jewelry. Used literary in 1892 in G.F.Gee’s “The Jeweler’s Assistant”, the expression was first used in its figurative sense in 1912¹³.

2) Economic term – The acid test, or quick ratio, involves assessing a company’s balance sheet to see whether it has enough funding on hand to cover its current debt¹⁴.

Analyzing these examples, we found out that the chemical term “acid test” in the English language has been transferred to the economic term, that is, in economics, the term “acid test” is used to check the cash ratio and current liabilities of a company. Thus, the meaning of “test” in the terminological text, conditionally activated from a latent state, contributed to the emergence of a commercial professional expression.

In other words, the phraseological units given in the above examples acquired a new meaning, a phenomenon of reterminologization took place and began to be used in new contexts. So, we can see that as a result of the phenomenon of reterminologization, the functional-semantic range of the unit narrowed and moved to a new terminological system.

As we mentioned above, phraseological units occupy an important place in the language and enrich its expressive possibilities. This, in turn, serves the correct and emotional expression of thoughts and feelings. Reterminologization of phraseological units is one of the important processes that allows adapting the language to the changing needs and requirements of society and professional activity. This event contributes to the creation of a common language and ensures more effective communication within the professional community. Thus, understanding and studying the theoretical aspects of the reterminologizing of phraseological units is an important task of linguists and specialists in various fields of knowledge.

In conclusion, it is worth saying that the reterminologization of phraseological units is one of the complex and multifaceted processes that affect the development of language and society as a whole. It is related to sociolinguistic and linguistic changes and has practical applications in various fields of activity. Understanding and researching this process allows for a deeper understanding and analysis of language phenomena, its impact on society.

12 Кунин А.В. Большой англо-русский фразеологический словарь: Около 20 000 фразеологических единиц. – М.: Живой язык, 2005. – 944 с. – 177 с.

13 <https://www.thefreedictionary.com/criterion>

14 <https://www.investopedia.com/ask/answers/011315/how-do-i-calculate-acid-test-ratio-balance-sheet.asp>